

Final Report: Value of Openness, Inclusion, Communication, and Engagement for Science in a Post-Pandemic World (VOICES)

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Project Information

Project Title	Value of Openness, Inclusion, Communication, and Engagement for Science in a Post-Pandemic World (VOICES)
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Lead PI and Institution	Juan Pablo Alperin, Simon Fraser University
Consortium Members and Institutions	Simon Fraser University, Canada State University of Campinas, Brazil ZBW Leibniz Information Center for Economics & Kiel University, Germany University of Sheffield, UK
Core Team Members	Juan Pablo Alperin (Lead PI) Germana Barata (PI) Isabella Peters (PI) Stephen Pinfield (PI) Natascha Chtena Alice Fleerackers Melanie Benson-Marshall Isabelle Dorsch Monique Oliveira
Project URL	https://www.scholcommlab.ca/research/equity-and-inclusion-in-open-science/

1. Project Summary (max 700 words)

A summary drawing out the key points and messages (what has been achieved and what did not go according to plan and why).

The VOICES project set out to explore whether the shift toward open science (OS) during the COVID-19 pandemic led to more equitable and inclusive research practices—and how these changes might be sustained post-pandemic. It brought together researchers from Canada, Brazil, Germany, and the UK to investigate how OS was conceptualized, implemented, communicated, and experienced during the crisis, with a focus on equity, diversity, and inclusion (EDI).

Across four interconnected work packages, the project found that the pandemic accelerated the adoption of OS practices—particularly preprinting, open data sharing, and public communication—while also deepening ongoing debates about the purpose of science and the structures that govern it. While many stakeholders recognized the societal value of openness during the pandemic, concerns about misinformation and quality control became more pronounced, especially in relation to preprints.

Work Package 1 (WP1) analyzed how OS was framed during and after the peak of the pandemic across different linguistic and regional contexts, with a focus on whether these framings reflected commitments to participatory and inclusive research. Drawing on qualitative content analysis of over 440 multilingual documents and 31 expert interviews, the study found that while OS was commonly promoted as a public good, understandings and enactments of openness varied substantially. These variations highlight the importance of context-sensitive approaches in future OS policy, particularly if equity and inclusion are to be meaningfully addressed.

WP2 examined how open access (OA) publishing shifted during the pandemic through a comparative analysis of COVID-19 and non-COVID-19 research from 2016 to 2023. COVID-19 publications were more likely to be openly accessible, especially through Bronze and Gold OA. These publications were also more likely to appear in lower-impact journals, involve early-career researchers, and come from international teams, pointing to patterns shaped by urgency and uneven access to publishing opportunities (in preparation). In parallel, a mapping of scholarly literature on OS revealed a tightly connected core of OS topics and several more isolated areas, pointing to uneven engagement across openness dimensions. Together, the results highlight the need for more durable, inclusive, and coordinated OS policies and infrastructure for scholarly publishing.

WP3 explored how OS and public science communication intersected in the context of press releases and media reporting. It found that Science news agencies (SNA) played an important role in making research accessible—particularly by summarizing paywalled

articles—yet their press releases were often written for journalists. Although these releases were also accessed by the public, their journalistic framing limited their legibility to broader audiences. This underscores the need to adapt SNA content for wider accessibility. Research from WP3 (under review) also demonstrates that the surge of preprints during COVID-19 have increased concerns about misinformation, with important implications for OS policy and practice.

WP4 examined how both journalists and preprint platforms navigated the tensions between openness and credibility during the COVID-19 pandemic. While media coverage of preprints spiked early on, it declined over time—reflecting a reversion to established journalistic norms and increased caution around reporting unreviewed research. At the same time, preprint platforms came under heightened scrutiny and adapted their moderation practices in response. Two literature reviews highlighted both the value and challenges of OS outputs present for journalists—especially around access, credibility, and verification—and called for more cross-disciplinary and globally diverse research at the intersection of journalism and OS.

A complementary policy analysis revealed that EDI and public participation—values central to making science more inclusive—are largely missing or superficially addressed in OS policy documents, limiting OS’s transformative potential and pointing to the need for more transformative OS governance models.

Taken together, the project’s findings reveal that the COVID-19 pandemic acted as both a catalyst and a stress test for OS. While the crisis accelerated the uptake of open practices—particularly in relation to preprints, data sharing, and public engagement—it also exposed ongoing tensions around trust, verification, inclusion, and infrastructure. Our research, thus, highlights that openness alone is not sufficient. How OS is implemented and governed matters, especially in times of crisis. Responding more equitably and effectively to future emergencies will require integrating equity and inclusion into both policy and practice, investing in the infrastructures that support openness, and strengthening collaboration across research, policy, journalism, public relations, and the public.

These broader insights about the conditions necessary for meaningful openness were also reflected in the project’s internal dynamics. While the project was structured around interconnected work packages, we had initially hoped for more sustained collaboration across teams from early design through to publication. In practice, differences in research timelines and cultures, time zones, and institutional pressures made that difficult to realize. Still, we are pleased with how we navigated these complexities. The shared frameworks, joint meetings, and moments of alignment we built not only supported the work at hand but also created a strong foundation for future cross-team work.

2. Key findings

2.1. Project's research findings and outputs/outcomes

Key Findings:

1. Open science expanded during the pandemic—but unevenly

While the pandemic accelerated practices like preprinting, data sharing, and broader public engagement, the adoption of open science (OS) varied significantly by country, language, and research field. These differences highlight the importance of designing OS strategies that are adaptable to diverse contexts.

2. Open science is not one-size-fits-all

The meaning and implementation of OS during the pandemic were highly context-dependent. We found that while OS was widely framed as a public good, conceptions of what counted as “open” varied by country, language, and discipline. Equity, diversity, and inclusion were often not central to these definitions and appeared more as aspirational values than operational commitments.

3. Openness peaked early—then receded, with real-world consequences

Peer-reviewed coronavirus research was widely accessible at the start of the pandemic, particularly through Bronze and Gold open access (OA). This surge in openness was made possible by publishers temporarily lifting paywalls—a tacit recognition that openness accelerates scientific progress. Yet Bronze OA offers no guarantee of lasting access, as articles can be re-paywalled at any time. The scaling back of openness underscores the fragility of current OA models, the market dominance of publishers, and the need for stronger policies that frame OA as a durable public good.

4. Preprints offered speed but raised credibility concerns

Journalists relied on preprints early in the pandemic due to their speed and accessibility. However, concerns about credibility and the absence of peer review made them difficult to report on. As the pandemic progressed, use of preprints in media declined—likely, at least in part, due to concerns around misinformation that grew during the pandemic.

5. Science communication and OS remain disconnected

Press releases and media reporting often promoted the public benefits of openness, but they rarely addressed equity, diversity, and inclusion or made research content broadly accessible. Science news agencies played a key role in disseminating findings from paywalled journals, yet press materials were typically written for journalists. Though members of the public could also access these materials, their specialist framing limited their accessibility to non-expert audiences. Notably, we observed that Agência Bori (a Brazilian science news agency) launched during the pandemic that adapted press releases into formats more accessible to the general public. The divide between OS and science communication is also present within the scholarly literature, with very little empirical research examining it.

6. OS worked as a crisis response—but needs strengthening to work optimally

The pandemic demonstrated that OS can support more responsive, collaborative, and transparent science in moments of crisis. Still, without stronger infrastructure, fair governance, and attention to equity, the benefits of OS are difficult to sustain. To ensure OS can endure and evolve, inclusion needs to be treated as a central concern—not an afterthought—in both policy and infrastructure.

2.2. How did you go about in achieving your research findings and outputs/outcomes?

The VOICES project employed a multi-country, multi-method approach combining traditional and emergent methods in internal and external science communication research—including bibliometric and altmetric analysis, quantitative and qualitative content analysis, document analysis, and stakeholder interviews.

The research was structured around four interlinked work packages, each led by a country team (Canada, Brazil, Germany, and the UK), and supported by regular cross-team meetings. Shared analytical frameworks were developed collaboratively over time to support coherence across diverse methodological approaches and national contexts. Key moments in this process were two in-person meetings, in Hamburg, Germany, and Vancouver, Canada, where team members came together to align conceptual approaches and methodologies, discuss and reflect emerging findings, and set the agenda for future work.

To explore how OS was conceptualized and implemented during the pandemic, we conducted a qualitative content analysis of 446 documents in five languages, supplemented by 31 expert interviews (WP1). To investigate how open access publishing shifted during the pandemic, we conducted a comparative bibliometric analysis of

COVID-19 and non-COVID-19 research articles and reviews (n = 19,738,427) published between 2016 and 2023 as well as a mapping of research literature mentioning OS (WP2). To examine how OS was represented and communicated to the public, we analyzed 265,653 press releases based on open access scientific papers (WP3). To explore how OS outputs—particularly preprints—were taken up, interpreted, and governed during the pandemic, we conducted two media analyses of 94 English-language outlets, interviewed 14 preprint server representatives about moderation practices, and carried out two literature reviews on the intersections of OS and journalism (WP4). A parallel policy analysis explored how national and international OS strategies articulated (or failed to articulate) commitments to equity, diversity, and inclusion.

By combining diverse methods and perspectives, the project produced both country-specific insights and comparative findings, illuminating how OS was practiced, contested, and governed across diverse contexts during the pandemic.

2.3. Assess the Trans-Atlantic Partnership (what worked and didn't work well? What has been achieved through this joint funding that would not have been possible within a national funding framework? Do partners have plans to continue the cooperation?)

One of the project's greatest strengths was the diversity of expertise within the team. Researchers came from backgrounds including computer science, communication, information studies, science and technology studies, and publishing studies, and brought a combination of scholarly and professional expertise. While this interdisciplinarity enriched the project by allowing us to approach OS from multiple vantage points, it also generated friction, particularly among team members less familiar with cross-disciplinary collaboration. For example, early discussions revealed different assumptions about methodology, output formats, and epistemological starting points. These tensions required time, negotiation, and reflexivity, but ultimately strengthened the project by surfacing deeper questions about how openness is defined and practiced across disciplines and regions.

The international scope of the collaboration added another layer of complexity. Team members brought different national research cultures, institutional expectations, and communication norms. These differences occasionally led to misalignment—around timelines, feedback practices, or approaches to collaboration. At the same time, they offered important insight into how OS is shaped by local contexts. The need to navigate these differences deepened our understanding of openness as a situated, rather than universal, practice. This would not have been possible within a national funding framework.

Logistically, the project encountered challenges related to coordinating across time zones, differing institutional timelines, and administrative requirements. Each national team received funding and all administrative clearances at different times, and some teams

needed additional time to advertise, interview, and hire key team members (e.g., postdoctoral fellows). The result was approximately 8 months between the first and the last of the four teams being in place and ready to work. Such a gap, combined with coordinating across time zones, the varying nature of data collection and work for each work package further complicated synchronizing the activities across teams. Ultimately, while our hope was to work on a single project with four work packages, the realities made the everyday feel like we had four individual projects with some touch points to sync up results and support each other. Future Trans-Atlantic calls might consider centralized processes that remove bespoke local requirements for each partner.

Team members across the four countries continue to exchange ideas and are working together on select publications. Additionally, we are actively exploring new funding opportunities to extend the VOICES research agenda—particularly around the role of preprints and open review for advancing equity and inclusion in global OS governance.

3. Impact of the Project

- 3.1. **Academic impact of your project** (please provide a summary of the academic impact achieved. For example, conceptual impact (changes in the way researchers understand a particular field); new methods, techniques or classification systems; or training or capacity building within academia). If possible, please list the sources (publications, reports, reviews, web links, users/beneficiaries etc.) to corroborate the impact.

In terms of conceptual impact, the project advanced critical perspectives on the role of OS during crisis contexts, showing that while the COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the uptake of open practices, these changes were uneven, temporary, and often lacked integration with equity, diversity, and inclusion goals. Our findings challenge dominant framings of OS as inherently equitable or transformative, highlighting the importance of governance, context, and long-term investment. In particular, the project drew attention to how openness was often driven by urgency rather than structural reform, and how core OS values—such as participation and justice—remain marginal in both policy and practice. We also highlighted the overlapping goals of OS and science communication—such as their shared commitment to making scientific knowledge publicly accessible and usable—while drawing attention to the lack of coordinated thinking across these domains in research, policy, and practice. This work contributes to ongoing debates in science and technology studies, scholarly communication, and public policy.

In terms of methodological impact, VOICES demonstrated the value of cross-country, cross-regional, and cross-linguistic analysis in understanding how OS is conceptualized, practiced, and communicated. Rather than focusing on a single national case, the project drew insights by examining different policy environments, research cultures, and media systems in Brazil, Canada, Germany, and the UK. This was made possible through a shared analytical framework applied across several methods, including bibliometric analysis, multilingual content analysis, policy document analysis, and stakeholder interviews. By coordinating data collection and interpretation across national teams, VOICES became one of the few comparative studies of COVID-era OS that integrated linguistic and regional diversity into its research design.

Lastly, in terms of capacity building, the project supported early-career researchers and fostered interdisciplinary collaboration across information science, communication studies, science and technology studies, and publishing studies. Team members worked together to develop research tools, design comparative protocols, and co-author analyses. Regular cross-team meetings and two in-person workshops helped build shared understanding across disciplinary boundaries and research cultures. These activities strengthened not only

internal collaboration, but also contributed to a growing, international network of scholars engaged in critical OS research.

PUBLICATIONS

1. Chtena, N., Alperin, J. P., Pinfield, S., Fleerackers, A., & Pasquetto, I. V. (2025). Preprint servers and journals: rivals or allies? *Journal of Documentation*, (ahead-of-print). <https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-09-2024-0215>
2. Chtena, N., Alperin, J. P., Morales, E., Fleerackers, A., Dorsch, I., Pinfield, S., & Simard, M.-A. (2025). Towards an inclusive open science: Examining EDI and public participation in policy documents across Europe and the Americas. *Royal Society Open Science*, 12, 240857. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.240857>
3. Benson Marshall, M., Pinfield, S., Abbott, P., Cox, A., Alperin, J. P., Barata, G. F., Chtena, N., Dorsch, I., Fleerackers, A., Oliveira, M., & Peters, I. (2024). The impact of COVID-19 on the debate on open science: a qualitative analysis of published materials from the period of the pandemic. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 11(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-024-03804-w>
4. Chtena, N., Pasquetto, I., Fleerackers, A., Pinfield, S., Marshall, M. B., & Alperin, J. P. (2024). “Does it feel like a scientific paper?”: A qualitative analysis of preprint servers’ moderation and quality assurance processes. <https://doi.org/10.31222/osf.io/mp6ky>
5. Alperin, J. P., Shores, K., Fleerackers, A., & Chtena, N. (2024). *Stark Decline in Journalists’ Use of Preprints Post-pandemic*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10755470241285405>
6. Barata, G. & Oliveira, N. *Divulgação científica para o acesso universal ao conhecimento*. In: Crocco, F. L.T. & Jodas, N. (Orgs). Engenharia e Sociedade: Humanidades em Debate. Araraquara: Letraria. 2024. Instituto Tecnológico de Aeronáutica (ITA). Available at: <https://www.letraria.net/engenharia-e-sociedade/>
7. Barata, G., Oliveira, M., Peixoto, T., Almeida, C. C. de, Mazoni, A. F., Comesana, R. C., & Alperin, J. P. (2024). Comunicado de imprensa como indicador de atenção social qualificada da ciência: a construção de um banco de dados e suas potencialidades. *Liinc em Revista*, 20(1), e7046–e7046. <https://revista.ibict.br/liinc/article/view/7046>
8. Batista de Oliveira, M., Hafiz, M., Fleerackers, A., Bolonha Nunes, L., & Fernandes Barata, G. (2024). Science News Agencies in SciComm: an exploratory index for evaluating and enhancing public interest in mass-distributed press releases. In: *SciELO Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.1590/SciELOPreprints.9799>
9. Fleerackers, A., Chtena, N., Pinfield, S., Alperin, J. P., Barata, G., Oliveira, M., & Peters, I. (2024). Making science public: a review of journalists’ use of Open Access research. *F1000Research*. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.133710>
10. Fleerackers, A., Shores, K., Chtena, N., & Alperin, J. P. (2024). Unreviewed science in the news: The evolution of preprint media coverage from 2014-2021. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1–40. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00282

11. Oliveira, M., Barata, G., Fleerackers, A., Alperin, J. P., Falade, B., & Bauer, M. W. (2024). Bridging science communication and open science—Working inclusively toward the common good. *Frontiers in Communication*, 9, Article 1473268. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomm.2024.1473268>
12. Dorsch, I., Lemke, S., & Peters, I. (2023). Analysis of “open access publishing characteristics” for COVID-19 and cancer publications in web of science. In W. Semar (Ed.), *Nachhaltige Information – Information für Nachhaltigkeit. Tagungsband des 17. Internationales Symposium für Informationswissenschaft (ISI), Chur, Switzerland* (pp. 387–392). Glückstadt: Verlag Werner Hülsbusch. <https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10009338>
13. Fleerackers, A., Moorhead, L. L., Maggio, L. A., Fagan, K., & Alperin, J. P. (2022). Science in motion: A qualitative analysis of journalists’ use and perception of preprints. *PLOS ONE*, 17(11), e0277769. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0277769>
14. Oliveira, M., Barata, G., Hafiz, M., Marshall, M. B., & Pinfield, S. (2023). Pandemia trouxe oportunidades para mais inclusão na ciência: uma análise temática de documentos sobre práticas de ciência aberta. *RDBCI: Revista Digital de Biblioteconomia e Ciência da Informação*, 21, Article e8673918. <https://doi.org/10.20396/rdbci.v21i00.8673918>
15. Barata, G. F., Hafiz, M., & Oliveira, M. (2023). Relations between science and culture: twenty years of the Spiral of scientific culture. *MATRIZES*, 17(2), 121-132. <https://doi.org/10.11606/issn.1982-8160.v17i2p121-132>
16. Dorsch, I., Hare, M., Mongeon, P., & Peters, I. (2024). Mapping Open Science Scholarly Literature. 28th International Conference on Science, Technology and Innovation Indicators (STI2024), Berlin, Germany. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14163843>
17. Benson Marshall, M., Pinfield, S., Abbott, P., Cox, A., Alperin, J. P., Chtena, N., & Fleerackers, A. (2025). “It’s messy and it’s massive”: how has the open science debate developed in the post-COVID era?. *F1000Research*, 14(500). <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.162577.1>
18. Fleerackers, A., Chtena, N., Oliveira, M., Dorsch, I., Pinfield, S., & Alperin, J. P. (2023). *Open data journalism: A narrative synthesis of how, when, and why data journalists use open data sources*. SocArXiv. <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/wh8jx>

PANELS, PRESENTATIONS, TALKS, & WORKSHOPS

1. Barata, G., Oliveira, M. & Peixoto, T. (2025, May 27) What can press releases of news-agencies inform about science coverage? Presented at the Public Communication of Science and Technology Conference (PCST) 2025 in Aberdeen, Scotland.

2. Fleerackers, A. (2025, March 24). *Making research knowledge public: Using open science to support science communication*. Presented at The Open University Open Research Week 2025, virtual. [Keynote].
3. Fleerackers, A. (2025, March 13). Preprints in journalism: Challenges and opportunities for open science (communication). Presented at the Université de Montréal UNESCO Chair on Open Science, virtual.
4. Fleerackers, A. & Alperin, J. P. (2024, November 6). Preprints as knowledge translation: Another way of opening science to the public. Presented at the KT Connects Open Conversations about Open Science Webinar Series, Michael Smith Health Research BC, virtual.
5. Benson Marshall, M., & Pinfield, S. (2024, September 11). VOICES: The Impact of COVID-19 on the Debate on Open Science: An analysis of expert opinion. OpenFest, Sheffield, UK.
6. Dorsch, I., Barata, G., Chtena, N., & Hafiz, M. (2024, June 5). VOICES – Analyzing the Value and Effects of Openness, Inclusion, Communication, and Engagement for Science During and Past the Pandemic. BRIC 2024, Vancouver, Canada.
7. Fleerackers, A. (2024, June 4–5). Advancing a networked approach to equitable open science, National Library of Medicine, Bethesda, Maryland.
8. Fleerackers, A. (2024, May 2). Post-normal science communication: How crises spur innovation. Presented at the Australian National Centre for Public Awareness of Science, Australian National University, Canberra, Australia.
9. Hafiz, M., Oliveira, M., Fleerackers, A., Caetano, C., Barata, G. The role of science news agencies in science communication: opportunities, challenges and public access. Symposium of the Public Communication of Science and Technology (PCST) & NCSR 2024. Zacatecas, Mexico. From 10 to 12 April, 2024.
10. Barata, G., Caetano, C. A., Oliveira, M. B., Mazoni, A. F., Alperin, J.P., & Costas, R. Comunicado de imprensa: como indicador de atenção social da ciência. Latmétricas. Universidad de la Frontera, Temuco, Chile, from 15 to 17 of November 2023.
11. Barata, G. & Oliveira, T. Course: Science communication to amplify open access to science. Latmétricas. Universidad de la Frontera, Temuco, Chile, 15th of November 2023, from 3 pm to 5 pm.
12. Oliveira, M., Barata, G. & Chtena, N. If a scientific culture driven by open science had a model, what would it look like? 4S - Conference of the Society for Social Studies of Science - 4S, Honolulu 2023: Making & Doing. Hawaii, USA, from 8 to 11 of November 2023.
13. Peters, I. (2023, November 23). VOICES The Value of Openness, Inclusion, Communication, and Engagement for Science in a Post-Pandemic World. 23.11.2023, at Education, gender and health: an open science approach to address social challenges, Workshop, Valencia.
14. Lemke, S., Dorsch, I., & Peters, I. (2023, October 27). *Post-pandemic changes in the adoption of OA models – a case study on Covid-19 and cancer research*. METSTI 2023 Workshop: Workshop on Informetric, Scientometric, and Scientific and

Technical Information Research (METSTI 2023), London, UK.

<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10555358>

15. Alperin, J.P. (2023, Aug 23). Identifying science in the news: Another use of Altmetric. Lecture Circus: University of Pennsylvania. Online.
16. Dorsch, I., & Peters, I. (2023, June 15). Assessing the impact of open science publishing practices in the course of the Covid-19 pandemic. 15th June 2023, RRC, Bonn, Deutschland.
17. Fleerackers, A. (2023, May 25). Reporting research knowledge: A review of evolving norms and practices in health and science journalism. Paper presented at the Journalism Studies Graduate Student Colloquium at the 73rd Annual International Communication Association Conference, Toronto, Canada.
18. Oliveira, M., Fleerackers, A. & Barata, G. (2023, April 12–14). Bridging open science and science communication: A theoretical perspective. Presented at the Public Communication of Science and Technology Bi-annual Conference, Rotterdam, Netherlands.
19. Dorsch, I., & Peters, I. (2023, March 8). Open Science: Gleichberechtigung und Inklusion im Zusammenhang mit der Covid-19 Pandemie (Voices). Frauen-Vortragsmarathon 2023, at CAU Kiel, Germany.
20. Alperin, J.P. (2023, Feb 23). The true opportunity of preprints. Biteca. Colombia.
21. Fleerackers, A. (2022, July 19). Introducing VOICES: What happens when you “open” science to itself—and the public? Presented at The Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative (COKI), Curtin University, Perth, Australia.

MEDIA MENTIONS & PUBLIC WRITING

1. Miller, N. (2025, February 3). As the US government removes health websites and data, here's a list of non-government data alternatives and archives. *Journalist's Resource*.
<https://journalistsresource.org/home/as-the-us-government-removes-health-websites-and-data-heres-a-list-of-non-government-data-alternatives/>
2. Fleerackers, A. (2025, January 14). *Using open data to sharpen science stories*. The Open Notebook.
<https://www.theopennotebook.com/2025/01/14/using-open-data-to-sharpen-science-stories/>
3. Barata, G. (2024). *As revistas científicas e o diálogo entre ciência e sociedade. Na Edição: revista de divulgação científica da UEMG*, Ano 1, no. 0, pp. 24–27. Editora UEMG.
4. ZBW (2024). OPEN SCIENCE im Wandel. Eine Kartierung der Forschungslandschaft. In *Open – Der ZBW-Jahresrückblick*, p. 68. Retrieved from: <https://www.zbw.eu/fileadmin/pdf/ueber-uns/2024/jb-2024.pdf>
5. Chtena, N., Alperin, J. P., & Fleerackers, A. (2024, November 13). *Preprints at a crossroads – Are we compromising openness for credibility?* LSE Impact Blog.

- <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2024/11/13/preprints-at-a-crossroads-a-re-we-compromising-openness-for-credibility/>
6. Oliveira, M. (2024, July 23). *Nosso laboratório de inclusão é tema de reportagem na revista 'Humanos', do Sesc RJ*. Site LABinCC.
<https://labincc.labor.unicamp.br/nosso-laboratorio-de-inclusao-e-tema-de-reportagem-na-revista-humanos-do-sesc-rj/>
 7. Oliveira, M. (2024, June 3). LABinCC e os Caminhos da Inclusão na Ciência. *Revista Humanos*, Sesc Rio.
<https://revistahumanos.com.br/reportagem/lab-incc-e-os-caminhos-da-inclusao-na-ciencia/>
 8. Chtena, N., & Dorsch, I. (2024, March 13). *Open science policies: What about equity and inclusion?* ZBW MediaTalk.
<https://www.zbw-mediataalk.eu/2024/03/open-science-policies-what-about-equity-and-inclusion/>
 9. Oliveira, M. (2024, March). *A “estetização da inclusão” e o retorno à luta política: reflexões de estágio de pesquisa*. Site LABinCC.
<https://labincc.labor.unicamp.br/a-estetizacao-da-inclusao-e-o-retorno-a-luta-politica-reflexoes-de-estagio-de-pesquisa/>
 10. Oliveira, M. (2024, January). *Chamada de trabalhos para GT sobre cultura científica no ESOCITE 2024*. Site LABinCC.
<https://labincc.labor.unicamp.br/chamada-de-trabalhos-para-gt-sobre-cultura-cientifica-a-no-esocite-2024/>
 11. ZBW (2023). *Multiperspektivische Forschung zu Open Science*. In *Open – Der ZBW-Jahresrückblick*, p. 32. Retrieved from:
<https://www.zbw.eu/fileadmin/pdf/ueber-uns/2022/jb-2022.pdf>
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<https://podcast.zbw.eu/fos/2023/05/26/fos-29-der-wert-offener-wissenschaft/>
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<https://labincc.labor.unicamp.br/o-labincc-em-2023-producao-de-conhecimento-e-de-redes-para-mais-inclusao-na-ciencia/>
 14. Aguiar, O., & Fleerackers, A. (2022, December 20). *Introducing VOICES: Understanding equity and inclusion in open science*. Scholarly Communications Lab.
<https://www.scholcommlab.ca/2022/12/20/introducing-voices-understanding-equity-and-inclusion-in-open-science/>
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<https://www.ndr.de/nachrichten/info/69-Publish-or-Perish.audio1290804.html>

3.2. Impacts outside academia (please outline the main changes your project has brought about for people outside academia).

Although the project was primarily aimed at informing scholarly and institutional approaches to OS, it also contributed to policy and practice beyond academia. Project findings were shared with UNESCO's working group on OS policy instruments, helping to further position the UNESCO Recommendation as a key reference point and influencing ongoing international discussions. The research also helped lay early groundwork for an equitable OS policy at the U.S. National Library of Medicine, although that effort was put on hold due to policy restrictions under the Trump administration.

Some of the project's findings were shared with policymakers in Colombia and Chile involved in shaping national open science strategies. Team members also contributed to practitioner-oriented platforms, including *ZBW MediaTalk*, *The Open Notebook* (a widely used resource among science journalists), and the *LSE Impact Blog*, helping to make the research more accessible to policymakers, journalists, and institutional leaders. The project was additionally featured in a resource for journalists on locating open datasets, published shortly after several U.S. government data portals were taken offline. Elements of the research were also discussed with leadership at PLOS, as part of their ongoing strategic review—particularly in relation to their engagement with the Global South. Finally, in line with our commitment to openness, all project outputs were published open access wherever possible to ensure wider accessibility beyond academic audiences.

3.3. Any expected future impact of your project

The project continues to shape ongoing work and is expected to have lasting impact. Alice Fleerackers will present a talk on critical science journalism, including themes of preprints and open data, in a webinar for Australian science journalists in July 2025, and will participate in a methods workshop in Montreal in September 2025, where she will draw on approaches developed through the project. She is also preparing an NWO Veni grant proposal that builds on the project's conceptual and methodological contributions. Additional publications are forthcoming, including a comparative analysis of COVID-19 and non-COVID-19 literature led by Isabelle Dorsch. Germana Barata and her team have submitted several papers stemming from the project. These include a manuscript on science news agencies (SNAs), currently under review at *Cultures of Science*; a paper on preprints and misinformation, submitted to the *Journal of Science Communication*; and a case study of the Brazilian Bori Agency, which is in progress and will be submitted to either *Perspectivas em Ciência da Informação* or *Revista Intercom*.

4. Project Team

4.1. Did the grant support the professional development of team members? If so, how?

Four postdoctoral fellows and one PhD researcher played leading roles in research design, coordination, and the sharing of research results, gaining valuable experience in interdisciplinary, international collaboration. The grant also supported their participation in both regional and international workshops and conferences, where they presented research findings and engaged with broader scholarly and practitioner communities. These opportunities helped strengthen their academic profiles and visibility within the open science and scholarly communication communities. Some of the early-career scholars on the team have been invited to give keynotes, guest edit special issues, and consult on OS policymaking based on their contributions to the VOICES project.

In addition, undergraduate research assistants and information technology assistants were involved across country teams, contributing to data collection, analysis, and dissemination activities. Their involvement offered practical training in scholarly communication research, and built capacity for future work in open science, science communication, and policy analysis.

4.2. As a result of the research, have any team members obtained any prizes, awards or commendations? (Please only include information that is available in the public domain).

During the project period, several team members received recognition for their scholarly and professional contributions. Alice Fleerackers was awarded a SSHRC Postdoctoral Fellowship and later appointed to a faculty position at the University of Amsterdam. Juan Pablo Alperin received a Graduate Mentorship Award from the Faculty of Communication, Art, and Technology at Simon Fraser University. Isabelle Dorsch and Isabella Peters received the Best Paper Presentation Award at the 2023 ASIS&T METSTI Workshop in London for their study on post-pandemic shifts in open access publishing in COVID-19 and cancer research.

4.3. Did the project lead to any additional and or unexpected collaborations outside of the research team? If so, please provide details.

The project led to several new and re-established collaborations beyond the core research team. Dr. Alperin renewed a partnership with Anne Clinio (FIOCRUZ, Brazil) around conceptual work on OS. New collaborations also developed with Rodrigo Costas (CWTS, Netherlands) and Alysson Fernandes (CAMPINAS, Brazil) on research using the OpenAlex

database—this work is continuing across other projects. Team members also co-authored publications with Steffen Lemke (CAU Kiel) on Bronze OA publishing and with Fakhri Momeni (GESIS Cologne) on gender and publishing during COVID-19.

There was also collaboration with science journalists and editors at *The Open Notebook*, a widely used professional resource, which is expected to lead to future research on the intersection of journalism and scholarly communication. In addition, Madelaine Hare (University of Ottawa / ScholCommLab) and Dr. Philippe Mongeon (Dalhousie University / UQAM) joined the team for a study mapping OS literature. Hare also participated in the second VOICES workshop in Vancouver, presenting findings from her PhD project.

The project further benefited from regular exchange with Stefanie Haustein (University of Ottawa and ScholCommLab), who supported the work through her expertise in open access, open data, and quantitative methods. She visited the team in Kiel in June 2023, participated in the VOICES workshop in Vancouver in 2024, and contributed to various online and in-person discussions throughout the project. Together with Anton Boudreau Ninkov (Université de Montréal) and Kathleen Gregory (CWTS Leiden), Haustein also presented findings from the *Meaningful Data Counts* project in a virtual session (January 2024), which helped point to possible future research directions.

We also invited several guest speakers to contribute to the team's thinking. Niels Taubert (Bielefeld University) presented his framework for understanding change in scholarly communication in January 2023, and Kevin C. Elliott (Michigan State University) shared insights from his work on open science and research ethics in February 2023.

5. Conclusions (please provide a brief summary with the main positive and negative issues concerning your project).

The VOICES project set out to examine whether the rapid shift toward open science (OS) during the COVID-19 pandemic led to more equitable, inclusive, and participatory research practices. Drawing on work from four country teams and using a diverse set of methods, the project produced new insights into how OS was framed, implemented, communicated, and governed across linguistic and regional contexts.

While the pandemic did accelerate certain open practices—particularly preprints, data sharing, and public communication—these changes were uneven, often short-lived, and frequently disconnected from broader equity goals and structural reform. Across all four work packages, the project found that openness was often pursued as a way to increase speed and visibility, rather than a means of expanding participation or redistributing power. In many cases, the systems supporting OS were not designed to reach broader publics or to redistribute power within knowledge production. Much of the openness that did emerge—such as the widespread use of Bronze OA—was temporary, shaped by short-term crisis response rather than enduring structural change.

The project also underscored the gap between OS and science communication. Even as OS outputs increased, they were not always accessible or legible to wider publics. Institutional communication framed openness as a public benefit, yet rarely addressed the question of who could make use of that openness in practice. Journalistic engagement with preprints brought greater visibility to OS but also surfaced concerns around credibility and trust in science. The initial surge in media attention to preprints faded over time, highlighting the temporary nature of OS's prominence in the public sphere.

Overall, the project highlights that without stronger connections between open practices, inclusive governance, and public-facing communication, OS cannot fulfill its democratizing potential. Structural issues, such as uneven participation, lack of long-term infrastructure, and minimal attention to equity, continue to shape who benefits from openness and under what conditions. Without deliberate efforts to address these gaps, the promise of OS will remain constrained—especially in times of crisis, when equitable access to knowledge is most needed.

6. Recommendations for the Trans-Atlantic Platform

The Trans-Atlantic Platform is a valuable mechanism for fostering international and interdisciplinary collaboration. It has been especially effective in supporting early career researchers. To enhance its impact, we recommend facilitating connections between funded projects earlier in the grant period. Earlier engagement would allow for the development of cross-project collaborations and more sustained knowledge exchange.